

Retention and Disposal of Research Data: from current to best practices

Final report for the Institutional Underpinnings extension project:

*Retention and Disposal of Research Data - Confirming Obligations,
Establishing Practice*

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Executive summary

Modern research institutions face the prospect of the indefinite retention of an uncontrolled expansion of uncurated digital content associated with research activities. To address that challenge, the Institutional Underpinnings Extension Project “The Retention and Disposal of Research Data - Confirming Obligations, Establishing Practice”, has identified decision points related to the retention and disposal of data that arise while undertaking research and investigated the best practices around those decision opportunities.

Decisions to retain or dispose of data depend on knowing the properties of the data. Therefore this project is closely related to the Institutional Underpinnings Extension Project, “RDM Business Intelligence and Reporting”, which has focused on the characterisation and reporting of research data.¹ The interplay between the two projects is outlined below:

The Retention and Disposal of Research Data Project has:

1. Unravelling the “data lifecycle” diagram and identified operational opportunities for metadata enrichment and retention or disposal actions
2. Selected five of these operational opportunities and investigated current best practice workflows for those decision points within participating institutions
3. Identified the metadata required to appropriately sentence research data towards retention or deletion
4. Documented common challenges and proposed solutions to institutional adoption of these practices
5. Proposed following recommendations:

Recommendation 1: Data Retention and Disposal Policy

In order to make retention and disposal decisions, institutional policies and procedures must consider four fundamental sentencing states:

- A. Retained indefinitely (e.g., as State archives)
- B. Retained for a minimum retention period as per the State retention and disposal authorities
- C. Retained for a maximum retention period as per other specific requirements (e.g., consent condition for data collection, data sharing agreement for externally owned data)
- D. Can be disposed of, as no retention period applies, including cases where the minimum retention period has passed.

The policies and procedures need to recognise that the sentencing states of data can change.

¹ D Jung et al., ‘Business Intelligence and Reporting of Research Data’, *Zenodo* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076883>

Recommendation 2: Roles and responsibilities

In order to make data retention and disposal decisions, institutional policies and procedures must articulate the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders (e.g., Chief Data Officer, researchers). The roles and responsibilities can be documented in the following way:

- A. Prioritise and align the identified operational opportunities to existing institutional practices
- B. Develop best practice workflows at each identified operational opportunity
- C. Assign roles and responsibilities in the workflows.

Recommendation 3: Integration and automation

To enable efficient metadata enrichment, and retention and disposal actions, institutional systems must be integrated and automated. Automated actions include:

- A. Assignment into appropriate sentencing state
- B. Review triggers for future action
- C. Extension of the retention period
- D. Disposal.

Recommendation 4: Researcher engagement

The Australian research sector (Universities, research institutions and peak bodies) must devise holistic strategies to motivate, incentivise and enable researchers who are the key actors in research data retention and disposal decisions.

Recommendation 5: Community of practice

A community(-ies) of practice with representatives from key stakeholder groups across the institutions should discuss strategies for sector alignment around best practices in research data retention and disposal.

Introduction

The Australian research sector is facing the challenge of uncontrolled expansion and indefinite retention of uncurated digital content associated with research activities.² Institutional obligations and best practices are currently unclear on how to determine which subset of the digital content is research data requiring long-term retention and which only serves an ephemeral purpose. Further, responsibilities surrounding the selective content disposal actions are not defined and contribute to the confusion and therefore inaction.

On this basis, an ARDC-funded, institutional underpinnings extension project commenced in March 2023 to establish best practice guidelines for Australian research institutions surrounding data retention and disposal. This report summarises the chronological outputs of the project work packages.

Workshop 1 - community building

A half-day workshop was held on 18 May 2023 in Melbourne, VIC, to *identify the operational opportunities for metadata enrichment that inform actions for research data retention and disposal*. The workshop was attended by 31 participants, including 10 online participants, from 19 universities and organisations (Table 1). The participants represented various business units, including IT, eResearch services, Research strategy, Library, Data governance, and Records.

Table 1. Participating organisations at Workshop 1.

University	Other Organisation
Charles Darwin University	The University of Adelaide ARDC
CQUniversity	The University of Melbourne CAUDIT
Curtin University	The University of Queensland NeSI
Deakin University	The University of Sydney
Federation University Australia	University of Technology Sydney
Macquarie University	The University of Western Australia
Monash University	UNSW Sydney
Swinburne University of Technology	Western Sydney University

Operational opportunities identified

At the workshop, the workshop participants identified opportunities for metadata enrichment and selective data disposal during the life of a research project (see Figure 1). Their descriptions are outlined in Supplementary Table 1.

² A Soo et al., 'The Macro View 2022 - Total Australian Research Data and the Data Growth Rate', *Zenodo* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10202367>

Operational Opportunities for Metadata Enrichment and Data Retention or Disposal Decision

Figure 1. Identified operational opportunities for metadata enrichment and selective data retention and disposal mapped to the research data lifecycle stages.³ Indicative retained data volume changes with lifecycle stages are also outlined.⁴

³ Lifecycle stages adapted from: ARDC, 'Research data management framework for institutions (Version 2)', Zenodo (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433246>

⁴ The diagram is also separately published: D. Jung et al., 'Unravelling the data lifecycle', Zenodo (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076895>

Current practices

The partner institutions were invited to complete a post-workshop task to describe their current institutional practices at the identified operational opportunities. To make the task manageable, they were asked to complete this task for a subset of the identified opportunities that the Workshop participants selected as valuable for further investigation and discussion. From participant feedback, it is recognised that differences in participant’s interpretation contributed to the variability in responses. These include various business drivers for acting upon the operational opportunities, University policies vs. actual practices, and systematised vs. *ad hoc* processes. Note: The current practice scan represents the best efforts by the representatives from each institution and is not definitive.

The first operational opportunity considered relates to researchers requesting storage allocations. As shown in Figure 2, all institutions currently implement a version of the theoretical process identified at the workshop with some caveats and limitations. First, the partners indicated variation depending on the storage type. For example, research-specific storage requires a centralised provisioning request process but general-purpose file management systems (e.g., OneDrive) are self-provisioned. Further, three of the five partner institutions indicated that the completion of a metadata form is often the first step, where an RDMP is required for storage provisioning. Consultations are available at request and training is not tied to the data storage request process.

Figure 2. Operational opportunity 1: New storage request

The second operational opportunity considered relates to data that is not accessed for a period of time (Figure 3). UNSW and Flinders University reported having no formal process that maps to the Workshop response. The University of Sydney could report a similar process to the workshop response but indicated that it is only implemented manually on an *ad hoc* basis. UTS and the University of Melbourne described their processes for eResearch infrastructure, and not for IT-managed general-purpose systems.

Figure 3. Operational opportunity 2: Data not accessed for a period of time

The third and fourth operational opportunities related to staff onboarding and offboarding (Figures 4 and 5). partners reported that they do not have a formal process during staff onboarding where custodianship transfer is documented or retention and disposal requirements are assessed for the incoming data. However, partners reported the existence of local (e.g., Faculty, business unit, research group level) procedures that govern this. Also, as indicated in the University of Sydney response, the change in custodianship and incoming data associated with staff onboarding are captured in other existing processes including a Data Sharing Agreement (DSA). Similarly, the staff offboarding process is managed at the local level and partners rely on researchers to perform the necessary data custodianship transfer and/or disposal actions.

Figure 4. Operational opportunity 3: Staff onboarding

Figure 5. Operational opportunity 4: Staff offboarding

The last operational opportunity related to situations where externally owned data is received (Figure 6). Similar to the previous operational opportunities, partners reported *ad hoc* processes where researchers self-report their use of

externally owned data. None have reported a centralised, formal process where retention and disposal requirements for externally owned data are documented in relation to the dataset and actioned upon.

Figure 6. Operational opportunity 5: Externally owned data received

Workshop 2 - continuing the conversation

The second workshop was held on 24 August 2023 in Sydney, NSW, to discuss and establish a series of agreed best practices for data retention and disposal. The workshop was attended by 30 participants, including 12 online participants, from 16 universities and organisations (Table 2). The participants represented various business units, including IT, eResearch services, research strategy, library, and data governance.

Table 2. Participating organisations at Workshop 2.

University	Other Organisation
Curtin University	University of Southern Queensland ARDC
Macquarie University	The University of Sydney CSIRO
Monash University	University of Tasmania Microscopy Australia
The University of Adelaide	University of Technology Sydney NeSI
The University of Melbourne	UNSW
The University of Queensland	Western Sydney University

Retention and disposal best practices

In the second workshop, the participants discussed strategies for research data handling based on differing retention and disposal requirements. Although there are only two decisions of importance in this project: retain or dispose, five categories were considered for the workshop based on the duration and reasons for retention and disposal decisions (Table 3).

Table 3. Five categories of digital research content based on sentencing. Sentencing is the process of matching the agency's digital research content to a relevant records authority to establish its value and for how long it must be kept.⁵

Category	Description	Examples
No Retention Period	Data that can be retained or disposed of under the institutional normal administrative practices guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data that can be disposed of according to Normal Administrative Practices⁶ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> transitory material or short-term items copies/duplicates externally published material
Permanent	Data that must be retained indefinitely.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data required as State archives or permanent records according to the State retention and disposal authorities Data kept indefinitely as a persistent asset in the institutional data repository Data kept indefinitely for other ongoing administrative needs
Within Maximum Retention Period	Data that must be disposed of at the end of a prescribed retention period according to the data usage agreements or licenses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Externally owned dataset used by the institution according to the terms outlined in the Data Sharing Agreements Data of participants who withdraw from the study, at which event the consent form specifies data destruction Personally identifiable information that is past minimum

⁵ National Archives of Australia, 'Appraisal and sentencing', NAA (ACT, 2023), <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/disposing-information/appraisal-and-sentencing>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

⁶ National Archives of Australia, 'Normal administrative practice (NAP)', NAA (ACT, 2023), <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/disposing-information/normal-administrative-practice-nap>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

		retention period required for normal operation ⁷
Within Minimum Retention Period	Data that must be retained for the minimum retention period as specified in state retention and disposal authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data required by the State Retention and Disposal authorities to be kept for a minimum retention period (Supplementary Table 2)
Past Minimum Retention Period	Data can be retained or disposed of as it is past the minimum retention period specified in state retention and disposal authorities and is not a state archive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data that has past the minimum retention period required by the State Retention and Disposal authorities

Using these categories of digital research content based on their retention and disposal requirements, the participants discussed the nature of the metadata that could be collected and acted upon at various operational opportunities to distinguish digital research content based on retention and disposal requirements (Supplementary Table 3). Some metadata are collected but never acted upon (project ID, access restrictions, date of and reason for change in retention period). These may be supplementary metadata that are not required for decision-making but provide complementary information. For example, project ID may act as an identifying key to connect different data sources. It should be noted that the categorisation of digital research content in this way is not to be taken as concrete and final. It may be better described as *sentencing states*, which incorporate the idea of event- and time-based changes in the states of data. Post-workshop discussions have also refined these states into four, merging the Past Minimum Retention Period into the No Retention Period state. This is reflected in Recommendation 1 under “Challenges and recommendations”.

⁷ Auditor General of New South Wales, ‘Universities 2022’, *The Audit Office of New South Wales* (Sydney, 2023), 32, <https://www.audit.nsw.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/FINAL%20REPORT%20-%20Universities%202022.pdf>, accessed 31 Oct, 2023.

Workshop 3 - broader consultation

The third and final workshop was held on 16 October 2023 in Brisbane, Queensland, at the eResearch Australasia conference 2023, *to validate the project outputs with the sector and discuss pathways to institutional adoption*. The workshop was attended by 53 participants, from 24 universities and organisations (Table 4). The participants represented various business units, including IT, eResearch services, research strategy, library, and data governance. The project outputs were presented once again at a Birds of a Feather (BoF) session at the same conference on 19 October 2023. Note: as there was a significant crossover between the current project with the other IU Extension Project, RDM Business Intelligence and Reporting, the workshop and BoF session were jointly held for both projects. Therefore, some of the content in this section is identical to that in the Business Intelligence and Reporting final report.⁸

Table 4. Participating organisations at Workshop 3.

University		Other Organisation
Australian National University	University of Canberra	ARDC
Curtin University	University of Otago	CAUL
La Trobe University	University of Technology Sydney	CSIRO
Monash University	UNSW Sydney	Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research
The University of Adelaide	Western Sydney University	Microscopy Australia
The University of Melbourne		National Institute of Informatics
The University of Queensland		NeSI
The University of Sydney		Netapp
University of Auckland		Sax Institute

⁸ D Jung et al., 'Business Intelligence and Reporting of Research Data', *Zenodo* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076883>

Evaluating project outputs

The participants were presented with the operational opportunities (Figure 1 and Supplementary figure 3) and asked to individually identify the top five most important operational opportunities (The summation of the votes is given in Figure 7). The opportunities with the most votes were *Start of Funding*, *Ethics Application*, *RDMP*, *Storage Provision*, *Project Closure (End of project)* and *Offboarding*. The metadata enrichment and actions (retention or disposal) at these operational opportunities are deemed most important for institutional implementation.

Figure 7. Participant responses to most important operational opportunities. The participants were asked to select five. The categories with more than 15 votes are highlighted in yellow.

The participants were also asked to rate the usefulness of project outputs. The same question was asked to the participants of the BoF session. The results are shown in Figure 8. There was overwhelming support for the project outputs.

Figure 8. Participant responses to the usefulness of project outputs for their institution. Results from Workshop 3 (A; n=45) and BoF session (B; n=72) shown.

Institutional adoption challenges and proposed solutions

In Workshop 3, participants discussed common institutional adoption challenges and solutions for the four common stakeholder groups: Researchers, Division of Research, Library and IT (Table 5). It should be noted that while some stakeholder-specific challenges were identified, there were common themes for all stakeholder groups. Key lessons from this exercise were:

1. Roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders should be more clearly defined
2. Motivation for researchers needs to be formulated
3. Systems should enable and simplify policy and procedures
4. Automation is essential to scalability
5. Research discipline-specific considerations must be made
6. Sector-wide, and cross-unit alignment is essential for advocacy, both internal and external

Table 5. Institutional adoption challenges and proposed solutions

Stakeholder	Challenges	Proposed Solutions	Engagement strategy (elevator pitch)
Researchers	Lack of incentive	Advocacy for carrots and sticks (e.g. funder)	Business Driver <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Quality of Research Output ● Reputation
	Time and resource constraints	System integration to remove redundancies	Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research domain-specific considerations ● Effective IT support
	Lack of support	Self-service resources, support personnel	Methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Effective engagement with diverse stakeholders including Faculty, Research Office, CDO and others
			Assumptions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● There is a risk of inaction ● Benefit & cost can be quantified
			Goals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capture new projects going forward ● Review past projects ● Iterative improvement

Division of Research	Resource constraints	Machine actionable DMP	<p>Business Driver</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk reduction ● Cost estimation ● Response to emerging policies <p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RACI ● Benchmarking from the sector <p>Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-unit engagement ● Contextualise the need <p>Assumptions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competition for resources ● Data is growing <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incorporated into key performance indicators ● Recognition in risk register
	Unclear responsibilities	Cross-unit, shared vision, clear articulation of responsibilities	
	Alignment of priorities	Clear articulation of benefits (risk, compliance, impact), national advocacy	
Library	Unclear responsibilities	Cross-unit, shared vision, clear articulation of responsibilities	<p>Business Driver</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Demonstration of Library's value in research data management capabilities <p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-functional team ● Business Intelligence <p>Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify champions ● Leverage existing cross-unit groups <p>Assumptions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research data management is a library priority ● There is resource to undertake the work <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data-driven decision making ● Engagement that results in culture change
	Lack of support for broader culture change	Budget for engagement activities, use CAUL, national alignment	
	Low motivation	Funder advocacy	
IT	Unclear responsibility	Creation of and support for research focused IT, specialised data managers	<p>Business Driver</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cost & Risk minimisation ● Reputation protection <p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Current-state analysis ● Cost-benefit analysis ● Buy-in from stakeholders <p>Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-unit engagement <p>Assumptions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data is growing ● Legislation is getting more difficult to comply with <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Automation ● Scalable solution
	Unclear requirements	Co-develop policy and processes, RACI matrix	
	Lack of resources	Clear business case to the executives	
	Fragmentation of data / metadata	Defined data models	

Establishing a community of practice

At the BoF session, there was significant interest in participating in a community of practice (CoP) if established, to sustain and further develop project outputs (Figure 9). The interested participants were asked to complete a form to note down their contact details (n=44). Their affiliations are shown in Table 6.

Figure 9. Participant responses to the interest in participating in a CoP to sustain and further develop project outputs (n=75).

Table 6. Affiliation of the participants who showed interest in participating in the CoP.

University	Other Organisation
CQUniversity	University of Technology Sydney AgResearch
Flinders University	University of the Sunshine Coast ARDC
La Trobe University	UNSW Sydney BioGrid Australia
Monash University	Western Sydney University CSIRO
Queensland University of Technology	Department of Defence
The University of Melbourne	Microscopy Australia
The University of Queensland	National Institute of Informatics
The University of Sydney	NeSI
University of Auckland	Netapp
University of Southern Queensland	Walter and Eliza Hall Institute of Medical Research

Challenges and recommendations

The project has highlighted key challenges and recommendations in improving the research data retention and disposal practices at Australian Universities.

Challenge 1: There is a lack of clarity on which portion of the digital research content is subject to retention and disposal schedules (and there is no lifecycle diagram for the rest).

For example, if a researcher had used a shared instrument facility and discovered *post hoc* that the machine was not configured correctly, rendering any output obsolete, is this instrument data still considered *research data* that is required for 5 or 7 years of minimum retention periods? If the central aim of data retention is *to enable the justification of outcomes of research*⁹, it is reasonable to conclude that only the portion of digital content that serves this purpose should be considered research data requiring long-term retention. Although some Australian institutions' research data management policies reflect this central purpose, and the NHMRC recognises a curation process where researchers determine which research data and materials are candidates for long-term retention¹⁰, state retention and disposal authorities do not explicitly address the central issue arising from the definition of research data (Appendix 2).

It is, however, noted that normal administrative practices (NAP) may be the mechanism by which some digital research content can be disposed of, complementing the state retention and disposal authorities. Subject to each institutional policy, some examples of digital research content that can be disposed of under NAP include duplicates and published datasets. Currently, institutional NAP policies are limited to administrative records and do not consider digital research content.

Recommendation 1: Data Retention and Disposal Policy

In order to make retention and disposal decisions, institutional policies and procedures must consider four fundamental sentencing states:

- A. Retained indefinitely (e.g., as State archives)
- B. Retained for a minimum retention period as per the State retention and disposal authorities
- C. Retained for a maximum retention period as per other specific requirements (e.g., consent condition for data collection, data sharing agreement for externally owned data)
- D. Can be disposed of, as no retention period applies, including cases where the minimum retention period has passed.

The policies and procedures need to recognise that the sentencing states of data can change.

⁹ National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia, 'Management of data and information in research: a guide supporting the Australian code for responsible conduct of research, NHMRC (Canberra, 2019), §3.1, <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/attachments/Management-of-Data-and-Information-in-Research.pdf>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

¹⁰ Ibid.

Challenge 2: The roles and responsibilities of researchers and other stakeholders in the institutions are not clearly defined.

The Management of Data and Information in Research, a guide supporting the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research¹¹ states the responsibility of institutions on research data retention and disposal (§ 2.3): “Institutional policies should address the storage, retention and disposal of all research data, whether held in an institutional repository or externally.” It also states (§ 3.1): “Researchers have primary responsibility for deciding which research data and primary materials are candidates for long-term retention and wider accessibility.” In practice, however, the institutional policies and practices do not enable efficient decision-making around which digital content is to be disposed of and which to retain (and for how long). For example, how does a researcher determine and communicate which portion of their digital corpus are candidates for long-term retention or are required to be deleted? If they are “candidates” for long-term retention, does it imply that the institution should have a review process to determine whether the candidates are truly worthy of long-term retention?

This is further highlighted in the metadata required for appropriate retention and disposal decision actions (Supplementary Table 3). Some metadata are collected by researchers for immediate actions (e.g., data downloaded from a public repository for analysis, or participant withdrawal), and others are delayed, with diverse stakeholders involved (e.g., infrastructure operators and research administrators).

The lack of clarity on the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders contributes to and is compounded by the lack of integration and automation of the systems. The current practices at the operational opportunities reported by the partner institutions are *ad hoc* and manual, with no integration or automation. This leads not only to a scalability issue but also demotivates researchers who are the key actors of retention and disposal actions.

Recommendation 2: Roles and responsibilities

In order to make data retention and disposal decisions, institutional policies and procedures must articulate the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders (e.g., Chief Data Officer, researchers). The roles and responsibilities can be documented in the following way:

- A. Prioritise and align the identified operational opportunities to existing institutional practices
- B. Develop best practice workflows at each identified operational opportunity
- C. Assign roles and responsibilities in the workflows.

Recommendation 3: Integration and automation

To enable efficient metadata enrichment, and retention and disposal actions, institutional systems must be integrated and automated. Automated actions include:

- A. Assignment into appropriate sentencing state
- B. Review triggers for future action
- C. Extension of the retention period
- D. Disposal.

¹¹ National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia, ‘Management of data and information in research: a guide supporting the Australian code for responsible conduct of research, NHMRC (Canberra, 2019), §2.3, §3.1, <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/attachments/Management-of-Data-and-Information-in-Research.pdf>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

Recommendation 4: Researcher engagement

The Australian research sector (Universities, research institutions and peak bodies) must devise holistic strategies to motivate, incentivise and enable researchers who are the key actors in research data retention and disposal decisions.

Challenge 3: The current models of the research data lifecycle impede effective discussions about data disposal.

Most research data lifecycle models do not show data disposal, yet this practice occurs at many stages of the lifecycle. Further, most research data lifecycles are unidirectional and do not adequately convey the iterative process that researchers often employ, going from “Collect & Create” back to “Plan & Design”, as an example. Also, many research data lifecycle models do not reflect the changes in research data volumes associated with different phases of the cycle. Clearly, the volume of digital content and data associated with research activities increases during the “Collect & Create”, and “Analyse & Collaborate” stages. However, it is expected to reduce during the “Evaluate & Archive” stage. For instance, the digital content that is not considered research data (e.g., data from an unusable instrument run) or sensitive data with mandatory destruction conditions (e.g., personal information in consent forms with specific HREC requirements for destruction) is or should be disposed of before “Share & Disseminate” and “Access & Reuse” stages. Only a subset of the total corpus of digital content associated with research activities should progress to these stages. Many of the current research data lifecycle models^{12,13} do not reflect these practices.

The project has identified these challenges through a series of engagement activities. In Workshop 3, the participants were asked to score these challenges twice on a scale of 1 to 10. There was a strong agreement with the challenges documented (Figure 10A). While there were largely balanced responses, challenges 1 and 3 showed evidence of skewing towards requiring sector alignment (Figure 10B). This is consistent with the suggestion of using sector alignment as a business case resource for institutional adoption (Table 5), and great community interest in sustaining the sector alignment efforts through a community of practice (Figure 9).

¹² ARDC, 'Research data management framework for institutions', Zenodo (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6392340>

¹³ M. Cioffi & J. Goldman, 'Harvard Biomedical Research Data Lifecycle', Zenodo (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8075933>

Figure 10. Participant responses around whether these challenges are dependent on individual institutional processes or sector alignment

Recommendation 5: Community of practice

A community(-ies) of practice with representatives from key stakeholder groups across the institutions should discuss strategies for sector alignment around best practices in research data retention and disposal.

Conclusion

Modern research institutions face the prospect of the uncontrolled expansion and indefinite retention of uncured digital content associated with research activities. The Institutional Underpinnings Extension Project: Retention and Disposal of Research Data has successfully used the Institutional Underpinnings consultation process to identify common challenges the sector faces on what needs to be retained or disposed of, for how long, and why. The project has also characterised the decision points (operational opportunities) related to retention or disposal actions and investigated the best practices around them. Finally, the project produced five recommendations related to the institutional adoption of the project outputs, and, importantly, the need to continue sector alignment efforts through a community of practice. The successful project outputs and the significant sector-wide interest provide evidence for the validity of such an approach.

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Appendix 1 - Describing the operational opportunities

Supplementary Table 1. Descriptions of operational opportunities.

Phase of Research	Operational Opportunity	Description
Plan and Design	Start of Funding	The start of a funded research activity. Operational examples: New grant number, project ID, RAiD captured
	Ethics Application	Ethics application approved. Operational examples: new ethics approval recorded in the ethics management system, research management systems records ethics outcome against research project
	RDMP	A research data management plan is created. Operational examples: New RDMP record generated
	Storage Provision	Storage is allocated towards a research activity. Operational example: IT department receives a storage request from a researcher
	Researcher Engagement at Proposal	Research support team discussions that take place to guide a researcher through a particular research process. Operational example: Library engagement, online resources
Collect and Create	Facilities / Instrument	Data and metadata generated by a facility or instrument. Operational example: Microscopy facility acquires images and metadata captured - microscope type, wavelength used
	Data Collection	Research data generated or acquired through research activities. Operational example: researcher captures metadata associated with their research data etc.
	External Data Use	Externally owned data acquired by the institution. Operational examples: New collaborative agreement/contract and data brought into the institution.
	Changes to an ethics-approved study	A change to an ethics-approved study. Operational examples: participant withdraws from the study, a child reaches adulthood.
Analyse and Collaborate	Requests for sharing, access, new collaboration	A new researcher looks to access existing data. Operational example: New collaboration agreement/contract generated; IT request for additional access to data
	Data Cleaning	“Housekeeping” activities carried out by researchers on data systems. Operational example: Computer associated with equipment fills up, or data needs to be organised for productivity
Evaluate and Archive	End of funding	Completion of the final milestone as required by the funder. Operational examples: submission of the final report, sign-off by the research office in the research management system
	Regular Audit	Research administration, or IT audit of systems or projects. Operational example: research admin checking on research project progress
	Project Closure (End of project)	A research activity is completed. Operational example: Grant funding is finished, funding body receives research final report
	End of Retention Schedule	Data reaches its end of retention schedule. Operational example: dataset reaches the end of minimum retention period

Phase of Research	Operational Opportunity	Description
Share and Disseminate	Research Output Publication	The publication of a research output. Operational example: New journal publication
	Research Data Publication	The publication of a research dataset. Operational example: New record in institutional repository, DOI minted.
Access and Reuse	Orphaned data review	Orphan data identified on systems is assessed for value, retention and disposal. Operational example: Untouched research data is identified as orphan and assessed for re-use or disposal potential
	Reuse Review	Data is reviewed for its impact or broader re-use. Operational example: citation number review, DOI stats
	Post Publication Changes	Changes to the perception of the research activity related to the publication. Operational example: Paper retracted, significance realised (e.g., Nobel prize)
Administrative Processes	New Infrastructure	Acquisition of a new institutionally supported research data storage infrastructure. Operational example: IT implements new metadata capture for any research use of new infrastructure, system operator implements terms of use for the new infrastructure
	Infrastructure EOL	Infrastructure used for research data storage reaches the end of life. Operational example: IT contacts research users to migrate data to new infrastructure
	Onboarding	Onboarding of new staff. Operational example: New researcher record in HR or research administration system
	Offboarding	Offboarding of an existing staff. Operational example: HR or research mgmt system notifies staff exit, collaborative agreement/contract ends

Appendix 2 - Scan of Australian State retention and disposal authorities

Supplementary Table 2. Current legislative scan of Australian State retention authorities. National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) requirements are also listed. The source material is provided for each jurisdiction as a hyperlink. Note: This table represents the best efforts of the project team at the time and is intended only as a guide. The information presented here is not definitive or exhaustive, and readers must satisfy themselves with the currency of the information presented here.

	NHMRC	NSW	VIC	QLD	SA	WA	TAS
Significant research*	Permanent	Permanent	Permanent	Permanent	Permanent	Permanent	Permanent
High risk material research				Permanent	Permanent	50 years after the date of publication or conclusion of the project	Permanent
Clinical trials	15 years	15 years after completion of research activity or when participant reaches 25 years of age, whichever is longer	15 years after completion of research activity	15 years after trial completion and 10 years after last patient service provision	15 years after action completed	15 years after the date of publication or conclusion of the project	15 years after trial completion and 10 years after last patient service provision
Research with minors			15 years after participant reaches 18			7 years after publication or project completion or when participant reaches 25 years of age	
Short term research	12 months after the completion of the project				12 months after last action	12 months after the completion of the project	
Large scale dataset for future use						12 months after last action	
All other research	5 years after publication	5 years project completed	5 years after completion of the research activity	5 years after last action	5 years after date of publication or 5 years after conclusion or abandonment of project	7 years after date of publication, or conclusion of the project	5 years after conclusion or abandonment of the project or date of publication
All other research resulting in patent				7 years after expiry of patent	7 years after expiry of patent		7 years after expiry of patent

*Data and datasets created as part of research activities within the institution, which are of regulatory or community significance, including gene therapy.

Appendix 3 - Metadata mapping to operational opportunities

Supplementary Table 3. Metadata that needs to be collected or acted upon at operational opportunities throughout the research data “lifecycle” stages to distinguish digital research content based on retention and disposal requirements. Some operational opportunities can be used to build a research data metadata record (**Collect**), whilst others can be used to trigger an action on the data (**Action**). Descriptions of each operational opportunity are available in the Supplementary Table 1.

		Plan & Design					Collect & Create			Analyse & Collaborate		Evaluate & Archive		Share & Disseminate	Access & Reuse			Administrative Processes		
		Start of Funding	Ethics	RDMP	Storage Provision or requests	Researcher engagement at proposal	Changes to an ethics-approved study	Data Collection	Instruments or facilities	Request for sharing, access or new collaboration	External Data Use	End of Funding	End of project	Publication	Post Publication changes	End of Retention Schedule	Reuse assessment	Infrastructure EOL	Staff Offboarding	Change in project stewardship
No retention period	Publicly available dataset							Collect Action												
	Duplicate							Collect Action	Collect Action											
Permanent	State archive	Collect	Collect	Collect										Action	Collect					
	Impact / Significance			Collect		Collect				Collect					Action	Action	Action			
	Primary Source			Collect	Collect					Collect						Action				
	Location of publication			Collect	Collect										Action					
	Is it FAIR			Collect	Collect										Action	Action	Action			
Maximum retention period	HREC ID		Collect	Collect	Collect	Collect	Collect			Action	Collect			Collect					Collect	Collect
	Participant withdrawal						Collect Action													
	External Dataset		Collect	Collect	Collect	Collect					Collect	Action	Action	Action						

		Plan & Design					Collect & Create			Analyse & Collaborate		Evaluate & Archive		Share & Disseminate	Access & Reuse			Administrative Processes		
		Start of Funding	Ethics	RDMP	Storage Provision or requests	Researcher engagement at proposal	Changes to an ethics-approved study	Data Collection	Instruments or facilities	Request for sharing, access or new collaboration	External Data Use	End of Funding	End of project	Publication	Post Publication changes	End of Retention Schedule	Reuse assessment	Infrastructure EOL	Staff Offboarding	Change in project stewardship
Minimum retention period	Project End Date			Collect	Collect	Collect				Collect	Action	Action			Action					
	Publication Date										Collect	Collect	Collect		Action					
	Date last modified				Collect		Collect		Collect	Collect					Action	Collect				
	Age of youngest participant							Collect							Action					
Common metadata	Project ID	Collect	Collect	Collect	Collect	Collect				Collect	Collect								Collect	
	Custodian	Collect		Collect	Collect	Collect			Collect	Collect	Action	Action	Collect		Action		Action	Collect	Collect	
	Retention Period			Collect	Collect		Action		Action	Collect	Collect					Action				
	Access restrictions		Collect	Collect	Collect					Collect										
	Retain Trigger			Collect	Collect				Action	Collect						Action				
	Delete Trigger				Collect				Action	Collect	Action	Action	Action							
	Date of change in retention period			Collect	Collect					Collect										
Reason for change in retention period			Collect	Collect																